
EARNINGS PREDICTABILITY AND STOCK PRICE: AN INVESTIGATION OF FOOD AND BEVERAGE MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT: The study examined earnings predictability and the stock price of foods and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Using simple random sampling technique, eight (8) companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) were studied. *Ex-Postfacto* research design was adopted and data were obtained from annual reports and accounts of the selected companies for the period (2014-2023). Dividend per Share (DPS) and Return on Asset (ROA) were used as the independent variables, while Stock price (SP) was the dependent variable. Two objectives and two hypotheses guided the study. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, and multiple regression techniques. The results revealed that both dividend per share and return on assets have significant effect on stock price of foods and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria, ($r = 0.565856$; $P\text{-value} = 0.0000 < 0.05$) and ($r = 0.766455$; $P\text{-value} = 0.0001 < 0.05$), respectively. The implication of the findings include that dividend per share can convey information about a company's future prospects, such as its ability to create wealth for investors, while increase in return on assets can signal to investors that the company expects strong future earnings. The study recommended that management should review dividend payout policy to remove uncertainty, and maintain consistent dividend payout ratio. Management should optimize asset utilization and management in order to maximize return on asset. These steps will keep stock price on the upward trend.

Keywords: Earnings Predictability, Stock Price Sensitivity, Financial Forecasting, Market Efficiency, Investor Decision-Making

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The interaction that exist between earnings predictability and stock price has been a subject of interest in the field of finance, with implications for investors, financial analysts, and policymakers. Earnings predictability refers to the ability of investors to forecast a company's future earnings. If the forecast about future earnings is positive the sensitivity of stock price rises. While stock price refers to the extent to which stock price reflect all available information about a company's future prospects in an efficient market. Stock price should reflect all publicly available information, including earnings forecasts, to ensure that investors make informed decisions (Gariffin, Kelly and Nardari, 2010). However, the accuracy of earnings forecasts can be affected by various factors,

including industry characteristics, macroeconomic conditions; social, environmental and legal framework, and the quality of financial reporting. These factors notwithstanding, the intention of every investor is to make returns. They have expectations on the value of their investment which propels their drive to make decisions on whether to buy, sell or hold particular investments. Zaki and Islahuddin (2017) maintain that investors want to minimize risks, while optimizing returns from prospective investment companies.

One of the ways to predict the profitability of a company by investors is to measure earnings predictors on the financial statements. Purdianto et al (2022) infer that stock investment is almost impossible without financial accounting information that accurate and timely which enable investor to settle on the best decision. Hidayyat et al (2021); Al-Matari, Al-Swidi and Fadzil (2014) and Ur Rehman et al (2014), recognize that there are various earning indicators or measure which can be utilized to evaluate the financial strength of firm. A portion of the indicators or financial variables distinguished include: return on assets, return on equity, Tobin-q, net profit margin, earnings per share, dividend per share, divided yield, price-earnings ratio, operating cash flow, return on assets and return on capital employed. This work utilizes dividend per share and return on assets as proxies for earnings predictors. The study intends to assess the effect of these earnings predictors on the stock price of foods and beverage manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Ideally, the stock price of firms in the food and beverage industry in Nigeria will be that the stock price is stable, growing, and reflective of the true value of the companies. This will indicate a healthy and competitive industry. The stock price will be influenced by factors such as dividend per share and return on assets; consistent sales growth, increasing net income, high return on equity, and growing earnings per share. These factors will attract investors, leading to an increase in demand for the stocks and subsequently driving up their prices. However, the industry faces various challenges, including fluctuating commodity prices, changing consumer preferences, and intense competition. These challenges have direct impact on the stock price of food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria. It has been subject to fluctuations due to various factors such as harsh economic realities, changes in consumer preferences, and competition. The Nigerian stock market, particularly the food and beverage sector, has experienced negative trends such as decreasing sales, lower profitability, or increased competition. Meanwhile, considering stock market dynamics, stock price can change rapidly in response to new information, events, or changes in investor interests.

Consequently, it is crucial to conduct regular studies or analyses of prevailing developments in the subsector and in order to understand how earnings predictors such as dividend per share and return on assets affect the stock price of food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This research aimed to fill this knowledge gap hence, the general objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of earnings predictors on stock price of foods and beverage manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Ascertain the effect of dividend per share on stock price ;
- ii. Assess the effect of return on asset on stock price.

Statement of hypothesis were formulated in line with the specific objectives and were stated in the null forms as follows:

- i. Dividend per share has no significant effect on stock price.

ii. Return on asset has no significant effect on stock price.

This study is significant to the management, investors, regulators and academic researchers. These stakeholders will benefit from the study by leveraging the findings and recommendation of the study during profit planning, dividend policy, investment, and assets management decisions. It will help the regulatory control and encourage manufacturing companies in ways that will boost their market stake and create healthy competition for economic growth, while serving as a valuable resource to be consulted by researchers.

The scope of the study was limited to earning predictability and stock price of foods and beverage companies in Nigeria from 2014 to 2023. Eight companies were sampled. Data were sourced from the sampled companies to conduct analysis of the study. Dividend per share and return on assets were the independent variables while stock price was the independent variable.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Earnings Predictors

Earnings predictors refer to the elements that hints or defines an individuals or organization's financial earnings or profits. These variables can be categorized into internal and external factors, and they play a crucial role in determining the financial performance and sustainability of a business or individual. According to Ross et al. (2019), internal earnings predictors include firm-specific characteristics such as management efficiency, corporate governance, and operational efficiency. These factors are within the control of the organization and can be managed to optimize earnings.

On the other hand, external earnings predictors are beyond the control of the organization and include factors such as economic conditions, industry trends, market demand, and government policies (Brealey et al., 2020). These external factors can significantly impact an organization's earnings and require adaptive strategies to mitigate their effects. Authors such as Penman (2013) and Easton et al. (2017) emphasize the importance of accounting-based earnings predictors, including revenue growth, profit margins, and return on equity. These variables provide valuable insights into a company's financial performance and are often used by investors and analysts to evaluate earnings quality. Additionally, market-based earnings predictors, such as stock price and earnings surprises, also influence earnings (Dechow et al., 2010). These variables reflect market expectations and reactions to a company's financial performance in addition to the impact of non-financial earnings predictors, such as corporate social responsibility, environmental sustainability, and governance, on financial performance which has gained attention (Eccles et al., 2014; Dhaliwal et al., 2011).

Dividend per Share (DPS)

Dividend per Share (DPS) is a critical financial metric that represents the amount of dividend distributed to each outstanding share of a company's common stock. It serves as an indicator of a company's profitability and its ability to distribute earnings to shareholders. According to Penman (2013; Ross et al. (2019) and Brealey et al (2020), DPS is calculated by dividing the total dividends paid by the total number of outstanding shares. This calculation provides insight into the actual return on investment for shareholders. A higher DPS generally indicates a higher return on investment, making the stock more attractive to income-seeking investors. As noted

by Penman (2013), DPS is closely linked to a company's earnings and payout policy. Companies with consistent and high DPS are often viewed as financially stable and committed to rewarding shareholders.

Return on Asset (ROA)

Return on assets (ROA) is a financial ratio that indicates how profitable a company is relative to its total assets. Comparing profits to revenue is a useful operational metric but comparing them to the resources a company used to earn those displays the feasibility of that company's existence. Return on assets reveals what earnings are generated from invested capital or assets. Dechow et al. (2010) discuss the importance of ROA in evaluating earnings quality. A high ROA may indicate high-quality earnings, while a low ROA may signal potential earnings management issues. As noted by Easton et al. (2017), ROA is also useful in comparing a company's profitability across time and against industry peers. This comparative analysis helps identify trends and areas for improvement.

Stock Price

The concept of stock price refers to the current market value of a single share of a company's stock, which is traded on a stock exchange. Reports of Samuelson and Nordhaus (2010); and Zaki and Islahuddin, (2017) suggest that stock prices reflect the market's expectations of a company's future earnings and dividends. So, stock price is a reflection of the company's value – what the public is willing to pay for a piece of the company. Graham and Dodd (2004); Shiller (2005); and Sari and Salam, (2019) have a convergent view that stock prices are determined by the interaction of supply and demand forces in the market, contending that stock prices can deviate from their intrinsic value due to market inefficiencies and emotional decision-making by investors. The concept of stock price is complex as it is influenced by various market, economic, and company-specific factors. On their part, Brealey, Myers, and Allen (2011) highlight that stock prices are influenced by factors such as interest rates, inflation, and risk perception. Conversely, company-specific events, such as mergers and acquisitions, dividend announcements, and earnings surprises can affect stock prices as well. The concept of stock price is complex as it is influenced by various market, economic, and company-specific factors. Understanding these factors is crucial for investors, analysts, and researchers seeking to analyze and predict stock price movements.

Theoretical Framework

Signaling Theory

The signaling theory was first coined by Ross (1977) who posits that if managers have insider information, their choice of capital structure will signal information to the market. The signaling theory, as it applies to stock market operations, suggests that corporate actions and announcements convey information to investors about a company's future prospects, which in turn affects the stock price. The main postulations of the signaling theory in the context of stock markets include information asymmetry. The signaling theory assumes that there is an information asymmetry between corporate insiders (e.g., management, directors) and external investors. Insiders have access to more information about the company's future prospects, financial health, and strategic plans than external investors. Another important postulation is the signaling mechanism. Last on the list is the signaling and stock price. The signaling theory suggests that stock prices reflect the information conveyed by corporate signals. When a company signals its quality, the stock price increases, and when it fails to signal or signals negatively, the stock price decreases.

Signaling theory, which explains how one party (the sender) conveys information to another party (the receiver) through signals, has been widely applied in the context of stock markets to understand how firms communicate with investors. However, like any theoretical framework, signaling theory in relation to stock market operations has its criticisms and limitations, which include the information asymmetry assumption. Signaling theory is based on the assumption of information asymmetry between the sender (firm) and the receiver (investor). Endogeneity and reverse causality. There's a risk of endogeneity and reverse causality in signaling models. For example, a firm's decision to issue a signal (like a dividend increase) might be influenced by its anticipation of how the market will react, rather than the signal being a pure reflection of the firm's quality or prospects.

Empirical Review

Dividend per Share and Stock price

Ahmed (2019) and Hassan (2019) revealed that dividend per share and earning per share have positive and significant impact on stock prices. The study further found that there is positive relationship between dividend and earnings per share. Finally, the study concluded that the findings over the effect of dividend policy on market price supports the relevance theory of dividend policy.

In their separate reports, Alajekwu and Ezeabasili,(2020); and Seini and Adebayo (2020) reveal that dividend payout ratio has significant positive effect on stock market volatility of non-financial firms, and positive but insignificant effect for the financial firms. However, dividend yield has insignificant negative effect on stock market volatility for both financial and non-financial services firms. It becomes advisable that investors in the financial services sub-sector should ignore dividend policies, in share pricing and evaluation of stock riskiness.

Aribaba *et al* (2021) examined dividend policy and share price of quoted companies in the Nigerian Stock Market. The study employs the *ex-post facto* research design. A sample of 15 companies was examined between 2014-2019 financial year using panel Estimated Generalized Least Squares (EGLS) regression with fixed effect. The study found that dividend policy and dividend yield contributes to share price reduction and were not statistically significant. The effect of dividend per share is negative and is statistically not significant across the quoted firms. Earnings per share were observed to result to positively engender share price changes but was not statistically significant; dividend pay-out and firm size positively influence changes of share prices of the quoted companies in Nigerian Exchange Group.

Oyedele and Afolabi (2024) carried out a study on dividend payments and share price behaviour of selected Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria. The study adopted *ex-post facto* research design involving annual data covering 2013 to 2022 time frame and across the 14 selected listed manufacturing firms. The data were obtained from the annuals of the sampled companies. The study deployed System Generalized Method of Moments (SGMM). Estimates of the coefficients of the model were evaluated at 5% level of significance. The results showed that dividend per share had significant positive effect on share price behaviour. The study concluded that corporate dividend payment is key determinant of share price behavior and that earnings per share and share price behaviour reinforced each other.

Return on Asset and Stock price

Dadang (2021) examined the effect of return on assets, firm size, and financing to deposit ratio on the stock price of PT. Bri Sharia, TBK. The study uses a descriptive method with a quantitative approach. The study uses secondary data obtained from the monthly publication reports and the monthly share price of PT. BRI Shariah, TBK, accessed from Yahoo Finance. Data analysis using multiple regression analysis with the aid of E-views 9 software. This study concludes that simultaneously ROE, Firm Size, and FDR have a significant effect on the stock price of PT. BRI Shariah TBK.

Syihab *et al* (2024) aimed to measure how much Return on Asset (ROA) and Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) effect PriceTo Book Value (PBV) in property and real estate sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2019-2023 period. This study uses a quantitative approach using secondary data from the company's annual financial statements. The population of the study was the 29 property and real estate sub-sector companies listed on the IDX. Purposive sampling method was employed to obtain the sample size of 19companies. The data analysis technique employed was panel data regression, through the aid of E-views 13 statistical tool. Results show that Return on Asset (ROA) has a negative effect on Price to Book Value (PBV) and Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) has positive effect on Price to Book Value (PBV), then for simultaneous testing it shows that Return on Asset (ROA) and Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) together have an effect on Price to Book Value (PBV).

Putri *et al* (2024) analyzed the effect of Return on Assets, Return on Equity, and Earnings per Share on stock prices in companies listed on JII for 2018-2021. It adopted an *ex-post fact* research design. Purposive sampling technique was employed to select 12 companies registered on JII for the period 2014-2018. The data analysis method used in this study is panel data regression techniques. The research results show that Return on Assets (ROA) has an effect on stock prices in a positive direction, Return on Equity (ROE) has an effect on stock prices in a negative direction, and Earning per Share (EPS) affects stock prices in a negative direction. The outcome implies that investors or potential investors should seek to know about the importance of analyzing the company's financial statements before investing.

To the extent of the reviews carried out by the researcher, while previous studies have investigated the relationship between earnings predictors and stock price across various sectors and countries, there exists a significant gap in the literature specifically focusing on the food and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The existing studies by Putri *et al.*, (2024); Syihab *et al.*, (2024); Ananda *et al.*, (2023), have primarily concentrated on the Indonesian market with a few studies conducted in Nigeria by Oyedele and Afolabi, (2024); Fijabi *et al.*, (2023); Aribaba *et al.*, (2021). However, none of these studies have specifically explored the food and beverage manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Furthermore, the review of related literature shows that scholars are in disagreement on the effect of some financial matrix on stock price. There is the aspect of Ahmed, (2019); Seini and Adebayo (2020); Tri, Abdul and Zulkifli (2022) and Oyedele, and Afolabi, (2024), whose position is that earning per share have significant impact on stock price s behavior, in contradiction to the position of y Aribaba, Ahmodu, Ogbeide, and Olaleye, (2021) who found that the effect of dividend per share is negative and is statistically not significant on stock price across the quoted firms studied. Therefore, this study aims to address

the following research gaps: Investigate the relationship between multiple earnings predictors (DPS, and ROA) and stock price. By addressing these gaps, this study seeks to contribute to the existing literature and provide valuable insights for investors, policymakers, and industry stakeholders by investigating the effect of earnings predictors, such as dividend per share and return on assets on the stock price of food and beverage manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) using a quantitative data analytics approach.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The study was an *ex-post facto* research design. Area of the study was Nigeria. Secondary data was the source of data for the study, obtained from the published financial statements of the selected foods and beverage manufacturing companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX) as at 31stDecember, 2024. Population of the study was the 15 listed companies. Using simple random sampling technique, eight (8) companies were selected. The companies selected included, Honeywell Flour, Flour Mills of Nigeria Plc, Guinness Nigeria Plc, Nigeria Breweries Plc, Cadbury Nigeria Plc, PZ Cussons, Unilever Nigeria Plc and Nestle Nigeria Plc. The following multiple regression model was developed based on the variables of the study: $SP = f(\beta_0 + \beta_1DPS + \beta_2ROA + \epsilon)$. Where: $SP =$ Stock price s ; $DPS =$ Dividend per Share; $ROA =$ Return on Asset; $\beta =$ Beta; $\epsilon =$ error term. Descriptive statistics were as well used to describe the data set. The effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable was estimated using a multiple regression equation for the analysis. The decision rule was to, Accept H_0 if the t-statistics is < 2.0 and the P-value is > 0.05 , otherwise, reject H_0 and accept H_1 . The stated null hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS

Data Analysis

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for the industry level data

	SP	DPS	ROA
Mean	-3732288.	-5234525.	3608842.
Median	746404.0	56170.00	-17888.00
Maximum	7168642.	9547751.	1.07E+08
Minimum	-1.02E+08	-1.04E+08	-22132965
Std. Dev.	18078111	20287034	20090362
Skewness	-4.093620	-3.311778	3.327136
Kurtosis	20.71435	14.40743	16.29261
Jarque-Bera	777.5260	355.2521	451.1531
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	-1.83E+08	-2.56E+08	1.77E+08
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.57E+16	1.98E+16	1.94E+16
Observations	80	80	80

Source: Author's Eviews 9.0 Output, 2024

The descriptive statistics in the table 4.2.1 presents the statistical characteristics of all the observations. These include measures of central tendency, the mean and median. Dispersions in the series are also indicated using the standard deviation. The results show the mean to stand at -373228, -5234525, and 3608842 with a standard deviation of 18078111, 20287034 and 20090362 for stock price, dividend per share and return on assets, respectively.

In addition to statistical description of the panel above, the descriptive statistics also test or checks for the normality of the observed variables. In other words, the test helps us to ascertain if the variables are normally distributed. To reject the null hypothesis that the data are not normally distributed, the JB (Jarque-Bera) statistics must be significant at a critical value of 0.05 (Gujarati and Porter, 2009). The normality test results reveal that there is strong evidence that the panel variables and dataset are normally distributed as the probability of JB-statistic for each of the variable is > the critical value of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected in favour of the alternative (H_1) that the residuals of the distribution of the model are normally distributed.

Table 2: Panel Regression Results

Dependent Variable: SP

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 12/20/24 Time: 10:20

Sample: 2014 2023

Periods included: 10

Cross-sections included: 8

Total panel (unbalanced) observations: 80

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
DPS	0.565856	0.100414	5.635258	0.0000
ROA	0.766455	6.731063	4.258547	0.0001
C	-770300.0	2083586.	-0.369699	0.7133
R-squared	0.803221	Mean dependent var	-3732288.	
Adjusted R-squared	0.792324	S.D. dependent var	18078111	
S.E. of regression	14113394	Akaike info criterion	35.80311	
Sum squared resid	9.36E+15	Schwarz criterion	35.88032	
Log likelihood	-875.1761	Hannan-Quinn criter.	35.83240	
F-statistic	31.75613	Durbin-Watson stat	0.793173	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000001			

Source: Author's Eviews 9.0 Output, 2024

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

From the model above, R^2 of 0.803221 shows that 80% variation on stock price (SP) was explained by changes in dividend per share. The adjusted R^2 of 0.792324 which considers more number of repressors explains that 79% variations in the dependent variable (SP) are caused by dividend per share and lagged values of share price. The results further indicate that the overall regression is significant as explained by the prob(F-statistics) of 31.75613 which is significant at 0.05 or 5%. This implies that the entire model is significant. Table 2 shows that the coefficient of 0.56585 is positive, the t-statistics of 5.635258 > 2 and the probability value of 0.0000 < 0.05 and significant at 5% critical value. Thus, the study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate that, dividend per share has significant effect on stock prices of foods and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

From the model above, R^2 of 0.803221 shows that 80% variation on stock price (SP) was explained by changes in ROA. The adjusted R^2 of 0.792324 which considers more number of repressors explains that 79% variations in the dependent variable (SP) are caused by ROA and lagged values of stock price. The results further indicate that the overall regression is significant as explained by the prob(F-statistics) of 31.75613 which is significant at 0.05 or 5%. This implies that the entire model is significant. Table 2 shows that the coefficient of 0.766455 is positive, the t-statistics of 4.258547 > 2 and the probability value of 0.0001 < 0.05 and significant at 5% critical value. Thus, the study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate that, return on asset has significant effect on stock prices of foods and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Discussion of Result

Result of hypothesis one shows that dividend per share has a significant effect on stock price of food and beverage companies Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Hassan (2019) who found that in the context of Bangladesh market, market price (stock price) is more affected by dividend payout than retention. It also aligns with the findings of Ahmed, (2019); Seini and Adebayo (2020); Tri et al (2022) and Oyedele and Afolabi (2024), those findings corroborate the position that dividend per share and earning per share have positive and significant impact on stock prices behaviour. However, this finding contradicts the result obtained by Aribaba *et al* (2021) who found that the effect of dividend per share is negative and is statistically not significant on stock price across the quoted firms studied. This contradiction could be as a result of data integrity and even the dividend policy operational within the companies selected. This is not also neglecting the impact of industry peculiarities, economic situation, successive government policy summersault and the state of security within the period that the study covered. This finding aligns with the signaling mechanism, one of the postulations of the signaling theory by Michael Spence, (1973). It suggests that to bridge information gap, corporate manager's use various signaling mechanisms to convey information to external investors. These signals can be voluntary or involuntary and include actions such as dividend announcements, earnings guidance, etc. it also considers signal quality, implying that the quality of the signal is crucial in conveying information to investors. Investors respond to signals by updating their expectations about the company's future prospects, which in turn affects the stock price. The direction and magnitude of the stock price response depend on the signal's quality, the investor's prior expectations, and the overall market conditions.

The result of hypothesis two shows that return on assets has a significant effect on the stock price of food and beverages companies in Nigeria. This finding aligns with the finding by Dadang (2021) that concludes that ROA has a significant effect on the stock price. This corroborates the result of the work by Putri *et al* (2024) which found significant effect of ROA on stock price. The above finding is in contrast with the position of Oladitire and Agbaje (2019) that concluded that returns on assets do not significantly associate with stock prices of money deposit banks in Nigeria. The above finding is in contrast with the position of Oladitire, and Agbaje, (2019) that concluded that returns on assets do not significantly associate with stock prices of money deposit banks in Nigeria. This position was further validated by the study by Kartawinata, (2021); Syihab *et al* (2024); and Vigar, (2024) who also found non-significant effect of return on assets on stock price.

5.0 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Findings of the study include that dividend per share has significant effect on stock prices of foods and beverage manufacturing companies in Nigeria, ($r = 0.565856$; $P\text{-value} = 0.0000 < 0.05$). Return on asset has significant effect on stock price of foods and beverage companies in Nigeria, ($r = 0.766455$; $P\text{-value} = 0.0001 < 0.05$)

The study adopted an *ex-post facto* research design to examine the effect of earnings predictors on stock price from 2014 to 2023. Eight companies were sampled from the fifteen foods and beverage manufacturing companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX) for the study. Dividend per share and return on asset were the independent variables (earning predictors) while stock price was the dependent variable. Descriptive statistics were as well used to describe the data set, while the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable was estimated using a regression equation for the analysis. Results show that Dividend per share and Return on asset has significant effect on stock price. The implication of the findings include that dividend per share can convey information about a company's future prospects, such as its ability to create wealth for investors. Increase in return on assets can signal to investors that the company expects strong future earnings. This signaling effect can influence investor expectations and, in turn, affect stock price. To this extent, investors should explore more options in determining investment destination. To this extent, investors should explore more options in determining investment destination, while management should device means to keep the explanatory variables on the real positive trajectory in order to keep stock value upwards.

The study recommended that management should signal investors through dividend per share. They can do this by reviewing dividend payout policy to remove uncertainty, and maintain consistent dividend payout. Management should optimize asset utilization and management in order to maximize return on asset to enable them drive stock price growth. This can be achieved through regular review of assets performance, discontinue the use of underperforming assets while investing in assets that can drive growth.

This work contributed to the body of knowledge in several ways. The study provides empirical evidence on the association between dividend per share, return on assets and stock price for food and beverage companies in Nigeria. This fills a gap in the existing literature, which focused on other industries and countries. This work also validate the importance of financial performance metrics such as dividend per share and return on asset in explaining stock price movements, reinforcing the notion that investors and analysts should not neglect these

metrics when evaluating food and beverage companies in Nigeria. The study further highlights the unique characteristics of the Nigerian food and beverage industry and its capital market.

This study provides a foundation for future research on the Nigerian food and beverage industry, such as examining the impact of macroeconomic variables on stock price. Further study can also be embarked upon to evaluate the effect of other financial and non-financial performance matrix on stock price.

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